

Open-source EDA software as a strategic alternative for European chip design

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Abstract. Europe's semiconductor policy has focused on fabrication, but chip design also depends on EDA software, a market dominated by proprietary US-origin tools. Because many of these tools are subject to the Export Administration Regulation (EAR), their use can add US export control exposure to European-designed chips. Many parts of the chip supply chain can still create legal risks, like PDKs, third-party IP, foundry equipment and destination rules. But open-source EDA may reduce export-control exposure at one specific point: the design-tool layer. Software that qualifies as "published" may fall outside relevant US and EU export-control rules. Targeted funding would not replace commercial EDA or make Europe independent overnight. It could, however, strengthen the design-tool layer, preserve European knowledge of EDA algorithms, verification methods, and design flows, and provide more transparency and reproducibility than a closed-tool-only ecosystem. This article examines whether open-source EDA can reduce that exposure in selected workflows.

Introduction

Integrated circuits are part of economic resilience, industrial policy, and national security. They are also dual-use items. The same chip-design capabilities that support cars, medical devices, consumer electronics, and industrial systems can also support military or terrorist applications. For that reason, semiconductor hardware, software, and technology often sit inside export-control regimes.

European debate has focused mostly on fabrication capacity and advanced manufacturing nodes. That focus is understandable, but the semiconductor value chain starts earlier. Before a chip reaches a fab, it is designed, simulated, verified, laid out, and prepared for signoff. EDA software is the working environment for those steps. It supports logic synthesis, physical implementation, verification, timing analysis, and layout across process nodes.

The EDA market is concentrated because the tools are hard to build. They require decades of accumulated engineering knowledge, large R&D budgets, and close integration with foundries and PDKs. These barriers have left the industry dependent on a small number of proprietary vendors, mainly based in the United States. In a stable trade environment, this dependence might be treated mostly as a commercial issue. Under current export-control practice, it is also a jurisdictional issue.

A chip designed and fabricated in Europe may still fall within US export-control analysis if specified US-origin EDA software was used in the design and the relevant regulatory conditions are met. The Foreign Direct Product Rules (FDPR) is the clearest example of this mechanism. In that setting, jurisdiction can follow the technology used in the workflow rather than the place where the engineers sit or the wafer is processed.

This article examines that problem at the design-tool layer. It looks at how the EAR interacts with semiconductor design workflows, how the concept of "published" software affects the scope of control, and where open-source EDA could reduce compliance exposure in selected use cases. It also considers what kind of funding and maintenance model would be needed to move open EDA from research projects toward industrial use.

Geopolitical context

Trade policy has moved away from the assumption that technology will circulate with limited friction. Tariffs, export controls, industrial subsidies, friendshoring, and reciprocity measures now shape cross-border technology transfer. At the World Economic Forum, WTO Director-General Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala stated that global trade was facing its largest disruption in 80 years [2,3].

For semiconductors, this matters because the supply chain was built around specialization. Design, IP, EDA software, wafer fabrication, equipment, packaging, and system integration are often spread across several jurisdictions. That structure works when rules are predictable and access is stable. It becomes harder to manage when governments treat technology dependencies as instruments of policy.

Export controls are one of the main tools in this shift. They no longer affect only goods leaving the regulating country. In some circumstances, they also reach foreign-produced items that are made with controlled technology, software, equipment, or know-how. Companies therefore have to examine not only where an item was manufactured, but also how it was designed and what technology was used along the way.

The European semiconductor position

Public debate on semiconductors often focuses on the race to the most advanced process nodes. These nodes are needed for the largest AI and high-performance computing chips, where transistor density is a central requirement. Europe has a different industrial profile. It has fewer customers driving very large AI data-center chip volumes, but it has a strong base in industrial, automotive, sensor, power, analog, and RF applications.

Those applications do not always benefit from further scaling. For analog, power, radio-frequency, image-sensor, and radiation-sensor devices, transistor density is often not the main design target. Voltage handling, breakdown margins, noise, matching, passive-device quality, sensing area, and power handling can all require larger geometries or specialized process options. In some cases, shrinking the device makes the product worse, not better.

This is why mature-node capacity matters. A 2021 policy brief estimated that nearly 50% of Europe's wafer capacity was at 180 nm or larger. [4]. That base is relevant for many European strengths, but it does not make the supply chain self-sufficient. Europe still depends on non-European equipment, PDK access, IP, advanced packaging, qualification capacity, and system integration.

Open-source EDA fits into this picture in a limited but useful way. It is not ready to replace commercial EDA for advanced-node, high-complexity chips. It is already useful, however, for selected mature-node flows, smaller digital blocks, mixed-signal support infrastructure, education, prototyping, and some early commercial work. Public examples include ChipFlow's reported 130 nm BCD automotive-OEM test chip [5] and a Dectris serial link in 110 nm CMOS [6].

Targeted funding would not make Europe independent overnight. It would, however, strengthen the design-tool layer and remove one EAR-related jurisdictional link in some workflows. It would also keep knowledge about EDA algorithms, verification methods, and design flows inside European research and industrial communities. A closed-tool-only ecosystem cannot provide the same transparency or reproducibility.

Consequences of non-compliance: risk, enforcement, and business continuity

Large economic powers project influence through capital, technology, supply chains, and regulation. Export controls are part of that projection. They govern exports from the regulating country, but they can also affect later transactions involving foreign-produced items derived from controlled technology or software.

Firms must classify technologies, screen transactions, manage licences, train staff, and document decisions. These requirements add administrative overhead, delay projects, and can be especially burdensome for SMEs. Consequently, non-compliance goes far beyond the administrative issue.

Under US law, export-control violations may lead to civil penalties, criminal penalties, imprisonment, and denial of export privileges. In serious cases, corporate officers and responsible employees may face personal liability. A

denial order can also cut a company off from items, software and technology subject to the EAR, which may be more damaging than the fine itself.

The indirect consequences can be just as serious. Investigations can delay shipments, block contracts, freeze financing, disrupt insurance, and damage relationships with customers and suppliers. They also bring regulatory scrutiny that can continue long after the underlying transaction has been resolved.

In the European Union, national competent authorities enforce dual-use controls under Regulation (EU) 2021/821 [7]. The EU framework is harmonized, but penalties are set by member states. Depending on the country and the conduct, sanctions may include administrative fines, criminal liability, seizure of goods, or withdrawal of export authorizations.

Enforcement examples from the United States

Recent US enforcement actions show how export-control rules are being applied in semiconductor-related cases. Administrative penalties issued by the Bureau of Industry and Security (BIS), the Office of Foreign Assets Control (OFAC), and the Department of Justice (DOJ) are public. They show the legal theories used, including reexport controls and the FDPR, and the scale of financial exposure.

Cadence Design Systems. On 28 July 2025, BIS announced a \$95 million penalty against Cadence Design Systems for unauthorized exports of EDA hardware, software, and semiconductor design technology to Chinese entities [8]. The DOJ announced that Cadence agreed to plead guilty and pay more than \$140 million in total for unlawfully exporting semiconductor design tools to a restricted PRC military university [9]. The case is directly relevant here because it involved EDA tools and semiconductor design technology.

Seagate. In April 2023, BIS imposed a \$300 million penalty on Seagate Technology in connection with shipments of more than 7.4 million hard disk drives to Huawei [10]. BIS described the matter as the first penalty under the Huawei FDPR. The case is not about EDA, but it shows how the FDPR can be used to reach foreign-produced items when the rule's conditions are met.

Applied Materials. On 12 February 2026, BIS announced a \$252 million settlement with Applied Materials, Inc. and Applied Materials Korea Ltd. concerning unauthorized exports of ion implantation equipment to China [11]. The liability was based on unlawful reexports of US-origin items. BIS also discussed the de minimis and FDPR frameworks, although they were not the primary legal basis for the penalty.

Strengthening export-control enforcement

US enforcement policy is also becoming more aggressive. In September 2024, BIS revised its voluntary self-disclosure procedures, penalty guidelines and created its first Chief of Corporate Enforcement. BIS presented those changes as part of a broader effort to strengthen corporate export-control enforcement and pursue more serious investigations [12].

The same direction appeared in congressional testimony. In written testimony before the House Foreign Affairs Committee on 24 February 2026, Assistant Secretary for Export Enforcement David Peters stated that BIS was stepping up enforcement actions. He cited recent penalties involving Cadence Design Systems, Exyte Management, and Applied Materials, and argued that export-enforcement penalty levels should be increased [13].

For business continuity, the message is direct. Export-control failures can interrupt operations, expose individuals to prosecution, stop shipments, terminate contracts, and restrict access to technology, capital, and insurance. When restricted parties or sanctions are involved, the consequences can include asset freezes or practical exclusion from important markets. For ASIC products, export-control disruption can also force design changes. Redesigning, verifying, taping out, validating, and requalifying an ASIC is time-consuming and expensive, and in some cases can delay a product by months or years. Such delays may also lead to termination of contracts with customers or suppliers, especially where delivery schedules, qualification milestones, or supply obligations can no longer be met.

Published technology and the limits of jurisdiction

US and EU export-control rules leave space for open scientific and technical communication. Under the EAR, information from fundamental research and educational instruction, as well as technology and software that is "published" and available to the public without restrictions on further dissemination, is generally not subject to the EAR [14]. There are exceptions, including certain encryption software classified under ECCN 5D002 [15] and specific controlled technical data or software, such as 3D printing files for firearms and related components [16]. The term "published" matters. In this context, it refers to information, technology, or software that the public can access without access controls or licensing barriers that restrict further dissemination. If software is published and therefore not subject to the EAR, it is not treated as controlled US-origin technology for FDPR purposes. A chip that is the direct product of that non-subject software does not trigger US jurisdiction on that basis alone.

EDA software as one possible jurisdictional link under the FDPR, showing how published open-source EDA may reduce the design-tool link to EAR jurisdiction while other export-control risks may still apply.

EU law contains a similar idea. Regulation (EU) 2021/821, Annex I, includes the General Software Note, which removes certain publicly available software from the scope of dual-use control [1]. The US and EU rules are not identical, and companies still need item-specific legal analysis. But both systems recognize that public availability can change the export-control treatment of software.

This point has older roots. The encryption-export disputes of the 1990s, including the Bernstein litigation, put source code and publication at the center of the legal debate. US courts recognized that source code can have First Amendment protection, which limited how the government could restrict publication. The analogy to EDA is imperfect because encryption software has specific EAR rules, including notification requirements. Even so, the episode shows why publication status can affect export-control analysis.

Open-source EDA is relevant for that reason. If an EDA tool is genuinely published and not subject to the EAR, then that tool cannot serve as the US-origin controlled software that creates jurisdiction under an FDPR analysis. This does not exempt the finished chip from export controls. It removes one possible link in the chain.

Extending export-control jurisdiction beyond borders: FDPR implications for semiconductor design and production

The FDPR extends US export control jurisdiction to certain foreign-produced items based on technological derivation rather than place of manufacture. A foreign-produced item may become subject to the EAR if it is the

direct product of specified US origin technology or software subject to the EAR, or if it is produced by a plant or major component that is itself the direct product of such technology or software. The applicable FDPR provision must also be satisfied, including knowledge requirements tied to restricted destinations, entities, or end uses [17].

In semiconductor design, this means that an integrated circuit designed and fabricated outside the United States may still fall within US export-control jurisdiction if it is the direct product of specified US origin EDA software and the other FDPR conditions are met. The design tool layer can therefore become part of the jurisdictional chain.

The inverse point is just as important. If a relevant software component is published and outside the EAR, it cannot create FDPR jurisdiction as controlled US origin software. That is the legal opening that makes open source EDA strategically relevant.

Open-source EDA does not make a chip immune from export-control review. PDKs, standard-cell libraries, third-party IP blocks, US origin cloud infrastructure, foundry equipment, Entity List restrictions, end-user controls, end-use controls, and reexport rules may create independent exposure. The better way to state the claim is modestly: published open-source EDA can remove one export control risk factor from a longer technical and legal chain.

Conclusion

The EDA market's dependence on proprietary US origin tools has consequences beyond vendor concentration. Under certain conditions, that dependence can add US export control exposure to European chip design workflows. As export controls become more central to technology policy, a toolchain choice can also become a jurisdictional choice.

Open-source EDA should be understood in that narrow but useful sense. It is a technical alternative for some workflows, and it can also reduce one form of regulatory entanglement where the software qualifies as published and is outside the relevant export control scope. That does not remove the need for legal analysis of PDKs, IP, foundries, end users, or destinations. It does reduce one dependency that Europe can realistically address.

For policymakers, the task is to fund maintenance, governance, validation, and industrialization rather than one-off prototypes. For industry, the practical path is gradual adoption in lower-risk and early-stage applications, especially where mature-node flows and smaller digital blocks are involved. For academia, the role is to keep developing verification methods, reproducible flows, and open research infrastructure.

Open-source EDA is not a substitute for the commercial ecosystem. Important gaps remain: access to advanced PDKs, signoff equivalence, analog and mixed-signal capability, certification, support, and foundry acceptance. Still, an open and maintainable design layer would give Europe more control over parts of the semiconductor design process. It would not be a retreat from global trade. It would be a practical hedge against toolchain dependence in a more fragmented regulatory environment.

Declaration on the Use of Generative AI

The authors utilized generative AI tools to assist in structuring the literature review, refining technical arguments regarding export control frameworks, and editing the text for clarity.

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